

ERA POLICY BRIEF

Interim policy report EUTOPIA – TRAIN

(DI.4)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework programme under grant agreement N° 101017419 EUTOPIA TRAIN

Carina Mallard & Sigridur Beck, University of Gothenburg

Corresponding author: sigridur.beck@gu.se

Website: <https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/research/eutopia-train>

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS ON THE TRANSFORMATION MODULES

GENERIC CHALLENGES AND HOW WE HAVE TACKLED THEM

Different structures, priorities, and concepts

Dissimilar organisational structures, institutional priorities, and definitions of key concepts within the partners creates an imbalance in priorities and resource allocation while navigating the complexity of organisational structures and counterpart roles.

Tackled: Mapping and analysing; engaging in dialogues at all levels, deepening our mutual understanding; sharing and aligning our interpretation of key concepts; using as a reference the good practices within our universities; creating openness, improving our communication efforts; and planning to increase mobility.

Covid-19

Covid-19 has made it more challenging to build relationships, connections or communities of learning and research and of management and admin staff, which are essential in conducting inter-institutional collaboration and development.

Tackled: Boosting the pace of the digital transformation process, focusing on online meetings, digital competence development and tools testing. Adapting and maturing our digital skills, working with teambuilding and ownership deepening, despite the lack of in-person mobility.

SPECIFIC CHALLENGES AND HOW WE HAVE TACKLED THEM

Developing a common R&I agenda & sharing of R&I infrastructure

We aim to generate a common R&I agenda that will make a difference and transform our institutions. We thus need time to anchor, discuss and debate the rationale behind the agenda and the benefits expected.

Tackled: By discussions and seminars during Eutopia-weeks and other fora, and by creating a specific task force of vice rectors of research to discuss and anchor progress at their specific institutions. In our [Report on Current Research & Innovation Strategies](#) we conclude that the focus on the common agenda should be on strengthening the preconditions of high-quality research & innovation and responsible research culture. This is to be further discussed and developed by the above-mentioned task force.

We have recently initiated the task of the infrastructure transformation module; this is according to the project plan.

Developing and deploying innovation strategies

The restricted information and contacts between partner institutions and their external collaborators has been identified as both a cultural and a structural challenge.

Tackled: By mapping the information that *can* be shared and ensuring compliance with the GDPR. By finding a balance between what data sharing is essential for our collaboration and what data is restricted and therefore, not shared.

Open science and citizens' science

Partners are at different stages regarding institutional policies, availability of staff and expertise for Open Science (including citizen science), as well as infrastructure for FAIR and open research data (all partners own interoperable institutional repositories for publications), and face national or regional contexts (e.g. legislation for infrastructure or training), though the differences are not extreme due to a common EU legislation framework.

Tackled: Launching the [community of practice on citizens science](#) to identify joint needs and challenges. Calibrating activities to be inclusive and beneficial for all partners, regardless of differences.

Strengthening human capital

Recruitment procedures are highly regulated and often involve policies and rules determined from outside the institution concerned, for example by national and regional governments. These sector specific regulations can be in addition to broader employment law that exists at regional, national and EU level.

Tackled: The tackling of this challenge could not be done through applying a common solution. Nevertheless, we have used bilateral agreements when applicable, as a way of dealing with the specific national regulations. This has increased our awareness of the importance of tackling specific challenges at European level with the objective of legislative harmonization.

Exploring joint structures

Different information systems, expertise of using these systems, as well as the resources allocated in the ongoing work with the systems, both in terms of alignment and updating them.

Tackled: We have tackled the challenge through developing and analyzing information gathered through surveys and focus groups. In addition, we have supported staff networking and created a framework that allows the sharing of good practices and development of a common working vision.

TANGIBLE PROGRESS & GOOD PRACTICES

Deliverables and other outcomes are and will be published on the community [EUTOPIA European University](#) (Zenodo).

Tangible progress can be observed, among others, in the following results:

- A signed memorandum of understanding between OPENAIRE and EUTOPIA to build the EUTOPIA Open Research Portal, aggregating and sharing metadata of research outputs from the different EUTOPIA university repositories.
- We made crucial steps towards an assessment system based around shared principles and dimensions of Open Science, implemented in a subsidiary fashion. This is implemented via a bottom-up process that allows staff and researchers from every partner to participate and contribute. First results are available in "[Driving assessment reform through collaboration – the approach of the EUTOPIA European University](#)" and "[From impact factor to responsible evaluation. Overview of developments in research assessment and implications for EUTOPIA](#)".
- The [online ATLAS](#) tool with information on incoming mobility opportunities to reinforce talent attraction and career development.
- The research & innovation services (GLENN) and the establishing of GLENN officers' roles, is a joint working structure meant at creating synergies among our universities' research and innovation offices building a common cross-institutional support system for researchers and support staff through a bottom-up process.
- The common infodesk tools (in a design phase) will be a one-way entry to GLENN, describing GLENN's services and providing links to GLENN Officers and tools.
- Members of the EUTOPIA [Young Leaders Academy](#) (YLA) is comprised of 19 members of early to mid-career researcher leaders, between 2 to 12 years after PhD completion, appointed for a period of 2 years. The program aims to support career development and research exchanges between high-potential, early to mid-career researchers from all EUTOPIA partner universities.
- [MSCA partnering tool](#), increasing visibility of the alliance researchers participating in MSCA post-doctoral fellowships calls and facilitating contact with potential supervisors in our universities (2nd pilot ongoing).
- Some institutions have implemented contact points for their Alliance to navigate the organisational structure.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The EUTOPIA-alliance deeply believes that solutions to contemporary challenges cannot only be engineered from the top-down. They should also be built from the bottom-up, in a flexible fashion, relying on the distributed expertise of various communities. Therefore, at the heart of EUTOPIA lies the conviction that we will only be successful if we create the conditions for our staff, students and partners to be themselves the agents of change

Policy topic 1: facilitating transnational cooperation

In order to facilitate transnational cooperation and synergies, regardless of it being joint degrees, digital or blended activities, challenge-based approaches, while acknowledging the work already done, we recommend further simplifications and sustainable long-term funding in order to embed seamless mobilities and in order to lower thresholds on sustainable collaboration on all levels.

We encourage the Commission to set up a stable funding scheme for the European Alliances, with medium and long-term objectives, covering all the dimensions (education, research, innovation, etc.). It would allow us to launch more ambitious actions and initiatives and will contribute to a more successful implementation of our activities and achievement of our goals.

We further encourage the EC to further support and fund initiatives (e.g. information hubs) for sharing information and experiences among and between the alliances.

Policy topic 2: strengthening careers

The EUTOPIA alliance does not yet have a common position on the European tenure track system. Even though we support the idea as such, we have not initiated work for a common tenure track within our alliance. We are nevertheless discussing the utility of an EU qualitative assessment tool of early career researchers. The tool could be used to observe national specific contexts within which precariousness occurs; evaluate early career researchers considering those contexts; and propose solutions to assure a comparative, cross-EU policies to tackle the problem as well as fair assessment of early career researchers when applying for EU funds.

New ways of assessing research. At this stage, the alliance has concerns about some features proposed in the Scoping report “Toward a reform of the research assessment system”. On the one hand, we think there is a contradiction between the focus on transformation and solution of global challenges in the European universities and a strict focus on 'metrics' which often favors existing research constellations and disciplines. Thus, a new form of research assessment is needed, that considers a broader perspective of a researcher's responsibilities, activities, and outputs. Aspects like reviewing and editing, supervision and mentoring, Open Science practices, and other services to the research and societal communities should be included. On the other hand, we consider that some quantitative metrics, such as citation index, are still important and relevant.

We fully support a multidimensional approach to assessing academic careers as laid out by the [League of European Research Universities](#) (LERU). Our own progress within the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project (mentioned above) is reflective of these principles.

Policy topic 3: digital transition

To accelerate digital transition in the R&I dimension, the alliances urgently need EU copyright framework in support of open science as well as that reform of research assessment is implemented at all universities of all alliances. Many EU Member States are establishing data centers or national Open Science clouds at national level. But to ensure all scientific disciplines are covered and to

facilitate cross-border collaboration of researchers using these infrastructures, additional distributed and interoperable e-infrastructures for data sharing, storage and management would be needed at the EU level. Even more pressing is the lack of data professionals (e.g., data stewards) that would support researchers in managing and curating research data. This requires continued support for EOSC at EU and Member State level.

The development of common open-source solutions should ensure interoperability of information systems, data management systems, data storage systems, use of API software etc. These practices should be comprised in a technical charter for suppliers and should become a minimum standard that would aim at supporting the digital transition in the R&I dimension as well as in education, outreach and general harmonization between alliance members. We recognize the need for the development of common European tools for digital collaboration in R&I and we call for the EC to address this need by funding and supporting the development of such open access tools and platforms that would facilitate cooperation across borders, sectors and topics. We encourage the EC to use the 41 existent alliances as pivotal input providers in terms of identified needs and constraints as well as actors willing and able to coordinate the development of such tools.

Aligning priorities between funders, governments and the Commission would accelerate the digital transition in the different dimensions, including R&I. We call for the EC to study the pathways to and lead the way towards a structured sustainable digital transition.

Policy topic 4: access to excellence

We encourage the Commission to support initiatives focusing on creating the framework for HEI's research & innovation services to reach knowledge required for excellence through participating in learning opportunities and sharing of experiences of those with a long track record of excellence.

We believe that we can focus more on increasing knowledge of the supporting services within research and innovation to give the researchers opportunities to excel in their research & innovation and thereby contributing to the European knowledge society and creating value for all its citizens.

European Alliances are the perfect opportunity to open excellent networks/clubs also to universities from R&I less-performing countries. We call for the Commission to support this opportunity by developing and including in its funding provisions that would stimulate the European Universities alliances to stay open to the universities from all parts of Europe in order to allow the exchange of excellent research and innovation practices and methodologies that can be found in any part of Europe, to develop common high ethical standards and processes, to enable the sharing of big research infrastructure and to provide funding of excellent research to all parts of Europe. Funding of excellent research and research support environment is crucial for access to excellence that is why national and European funds should additionally support the building of research support capacities of European Universities Alliances.

Cross-sectorial mobility

We urge the Commission to consider increasing cross-sectorial access to mobility to create good practices not only for excellence but also for regional cooperation, innovation – and in general for exploring each other's strengths and weaknesses, reflect and develop knowledge hubs and to share experiences at HEI level.

Complete Academic Environments

For the EUTOPIA-alliance complete academic environments contribute to cross-boundary research and collaborative education and are also characterised by cooperation with public and private actors from across society. This integrated approach capitalises on synergies and supports the development, evaluation and dissemination of new modalities and methodologies of collaboration. We acknowledge all current and previous initiatives meant to give access to excellence while we are of the opinion that further efforts that would link research, education and collaboration are needed in order to stimulate and revitalize access to excellence, in the context of the ERA framework for wider community expertise and excellence.

We urge for a common funding call that focuses on the importance of the interconnections between research, education, innovation and collaboration. As a good practice we would like to highlight EUTOPIA's Connected Communities concept which is based on the necessity of complete academic environments within HEI in order to bridge academia with other sectors and stakeholders.

Policy topic 5: increasing global competitiveness

To summarize – EUTOPIA believes that the following recommendations, already emphasized in the previous policy recommendations, will increase global competitiveness.

Cross-sectorial transfer/mobility

We believe that academia, industry and the public sector need to exchange good practices in order to come up with new solutions to old problems. We believe that the Connected Communities (see Policy topic 4) - provide platforms and co-existence that can facilitate cross-sectorial transfer.

The alliance would welcome the enhancement of funding frameworks specifically connected to the networking, exchange and transfer of experiences with academia, industry and the public sector.

New ways of assessing research & innovation

We encourage the EC to increase and continue the important support given to the concepts and practice of valorization of results, impact and cross-sectoriality and thus to strengthen those actions that would allow and prioritize cross-sectoral mobility and collaboration, awareness raising of the knowledge valorization importance, training on impact and sustainability.

Increase bottom-up funding for cross-sectorial collaborations

We believe that the development of bottom-up initiatives as part of the ongoing projects of the different alliances should be further stimulated and simplified so that to harvest the benefits of direct participation of the research field and adjacent sectors in the shaping the future research collaboration and impact.

Overall simplification of procedures

The alliance supports the simplification of monitoring and reporting procedures in connection with the researchers so that to equip these with more time dedicated to research activities rather than administrative tasks.